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PROBLEMS OF TECHNICAL TRAINING OF YOUNG HOCKEY PLAYERS

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Abstract

Hockey in Uzbekistan appeared relatively recently. The article under consideration shows the shortcomings in the technical training of young hockey players in the process of many years of training, the indicators for which our teams are inferior to the teams of the leading countries of the World are indicated. Recommendations are given for working on improving technical and tactical techniques that can help develop our hockey.

Key words: Technical preparation, maneuverable skating, power single combat, throw-in, defenders, forwards, technical methods

I. INTRODUCTION

Sports technique refers to the total mechanics and biomechanics of movements. The degree of technical readiness is assessed by the ability to use motor abilities, performing them in combat conditions in a limited time mode [1].

In the process of playing activity, strict spatial and temporal limits of motional techniques of hockey players, caused by the need for a timely reaction to the game situation and limited by the rules of the competition, establish the issue of teaching motional actions that dominate in the long-term training of athletes [2].

The modern high level of development of ice hockey makes special demands on the process of primary education of young hockey players. It is known that this stage is largely decisive for further sports growth. At the same time, the main place is given to mastering the technique of skating [3,4,5]. Therefore, already from the first steps of training, it is necessary that the educational and training process ensure quick and high-quality mastery of movements and be aimed at mastering the rational technique of ice skating, as well as virtuoso possession of a stick and a puck. During the game, the hockey player covers a distance of up to 10 km. A high degree of mastering the technique of skating allows the player to perform this load with the least energy consumption and at the same time does not limit his technical arsenal. Until a hockey player has gained confidence in his ability to skate, he will think during the game about how to maintain balance, about whether he chose the right way to skate, instead of focusing all his attention on solving tactical problems. Therefore, novice athletes must first of all be taught to stand well and skate, and only then to play hockey. Poor skating training is more difficult to make up for than any other component of a hockey player's skill [6].

II. METHODS

In the process of long-term training of a hockey player, an extremely important stage in terms of improving technique is the stage of sports improvement, which completes the high qualification of a hockey player and precedes the transition to professional hockey.

The technical training program at the stage of sports improvement includes (diagram 1):

- further improvement of previously studied stick and puck possession techniques;
- technique of power single combat;
- change in the direction, pace and rhythm of movement during the development and completion of attacks;
- implementation of technical techniques depending on the individual characteristics of hockey players;
- mastery of the technique of catching the puck “on oneself” (features of the technical technique of defenders and attackers);
- Possession of techniques for fighting for the puck during a throw-in;
- working on the individual characteristics of defenders and forwards during the performing technical techniques.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The whole arsenal of techniques should be performed at high speed, in conditions of time and space deficit and in the presence of confounding factors.

The problem of young hockey players who joined the team of masters is the lack of stability and variability when performing techniques at a higher speed than in youth teams. Therefore, the process of further improvement of the technical readiness of young hockey players requires additional attention from the coaches of professional hockey teams.

Diagram 1. The program of technical training at the stage of sports improvement includes

For playing hockey, technical training is the most important component. A tactical one is being built on its basis. preparation: the better the technique of skating, sticking, the higher the tactical education. This means that your team can use various tactical formations in the game to achieve a positive result .

Unfortunately , in our country little attention is paid to teaching maneuverable skating, stick handling.

Pedagogical observations have shown that our youth hockey is inferior to the leading hockey countries in terms of such indicators (diagram 2):

- 1) possession of maneuverable skating (for defenders and forwards)
- 2) possession of a hockey stick - wrist throws, hitting the puck during the move, finishing;
- 3) possession of the throw-in technique;
- 4) in most cases, power single combat are lost.

Diagram 2. Pedagogical observations have shown that our youth hockey is inferior to the leading hockey countries in terms of such indicators

The reasons for these shortcomings hite in the work of trainers on these techniques.

Pedagogical observations showed shortcomings in the work of trainers in the following areas.

1. At all stages of training - from initial training groups to groups of sports improvement - game method prevails training, as the head of the clubs put for the coaches of the groups initial training task to win every match, so the learning process is replaced by "training".

2. At training sessions in sports improvement groups, more attention should be paid to training and improving the possession of maneuverable skating.

3. When teaching tactical formations, mainly defensive schemes are used.

4. Not enough attention is paid to general physical training in weekly microcycles of the competitive period (out of ice).

5. Little attention is paid to learning and improving the game in numerical inequality (5x4; 5x3; 6x4; 6x5).

IV. CONCLUSION

1. In the preparatory period for the general preparatory stage technical training should take up to 100% of the volume of training sessions.

2. During the training and improving the technique of movement on skates, the repetition method and the display method should prevail.

All training sessions should include 2-3 exercises to teach or improve skating movement both with the puck and without the puck (for defenders and forwards separately).

Defenders' skating technique has its own peculiarity (they move more backwards), so it is necessary to select specific exercises for them. As a rule, in the game, the defender uses a number of technical and tactical techniques, to which the coach must pay more attention when learning and improving these actions, such as:

- 1) improvement of maneuvers facing and back forward;
- 2) taking the puck from an opponent (power of single combat);
- 3) the beginning of the attack (reception, transfer of the puck to partners);
- 4) support the attack (continue of movement);
- 5) throws at the opponent's goal (with brushes, hits on the puck, shots-kicks from move);
- 6) control the opponent (in own zone, in the middle zone, in the attacking zone);
- 7) interchangeability with partners (with a defender, with a central forward).

Exercises for learning and improving the maneuverability of skating:

- a) "X" - in face-off circles (with and without a puck);
- b) acceleration from the blue line to the red line, braking, returning backwards, turning towards the side;
- c) in the middle zone: from the blue line, accelerating diagonally to the red line, braking and moving backwards, turning on the blue line and moving forward (to the width of the field), 4 times backwards, facing forward.

In training sessions for teaching and improving the possession of maneuverable skating, exercises are also planned to improve tactical actions.

Technical actions for attackers:

- 1) possession of all methods of movement on skates;
- 2) taking the puck from an opponent (power of single combat);
- 3) dribble of the opponent (short, long, power);
- 4) receiving, passing the puck;
- 5) control of an opponent (power of single combat) ;
- 6) throws at the opponent's goal with various distances (wrist, puck shots, shots on the move);
- 7)“throw-in” for the central forwards

Techniques in improvement groups should be practiced at maximum speed with a shortage of time and space, under the conditions of confounding factors - the resistance of the enemy.

Work on improving techniques can be carried out not only in the main part of the lesson, but also in the final part (against the background of fatigue), for 10-15 minutes.

Practice shows that technical training is laid down in initial training groups (7-10 years old) and fixed in training groups (11-14 years old), therefore highly qualified trainers with appropriate remuneration should work in these age groups.

If this is not done, then young hockey players with an insufficiently high level of skill will appear in the teams of professionals, and this will affect the performances of the junior and youth national teams of Uzbekistan.

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